

ISMIR 2021 - Industry & Sponsorship Exit Report

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This document is an extended version of the **Industry and Sponsorship Activities** Section in the 22nd International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference (ISMIR 2021) Exit Report. It is intended as a self-contained reference for future organizers working on Industry and Sponsorship tasks in future conferences, including - but not limited to - ISMIR.

A summary of the contributions of the Industry & Sponsorship team in ISMIR 2021 is given below:

- Contacted around 60 prospective sponsors. Onboarded 20 ISMIR Sponsors and 7 WiMIR Sponsors.
- Secured a total of 92,500\$ contributions from sponsors
 - 71,000\$ for the ISMIR conference organization. 21,500 \$ for WiMIR and other diversity-related contributions.
 - To the best of our knowledge, we secured the most sponsors and the largest amount of revenue in any ISMIR.
- ~40% increase in revenue and five additional sponsors compared to ISMIR 2020, effectively returning the sponsor presence in the conference back to the pre-pandemic levels
- Four industry presentations, two industry panels, and two masterclasses in the conference program
 - Around 1000 people in total attended the sessions
- Implemented Sponsorship booths, job board, and CV pool in the virtual conference platform.
 - To the best of our knowledge, the job board and the CV pool were implemented for the first time in ISMIR.

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Team composition, labor division and timeline

In ISMIR 2021, Sponsorship and Masterclass chairs from the previous conference were merged under Industry & Sponsorship. The team consisted of 3 co-chairs: Sertan Şentürk (Kobalt Music Group), Alia Morsi (Universitat Pompeu Fabra) & Lamtharn “Hanoi” Hantrakul (Bytedance). The team's responsibilities were:

- Define the ISMIR 2021 sponsorship packages & benefits and supervise their implementation
- Organize and host industry panels, industry presentations, and masterclasses.
- Moderate industry & sponsorship-related activities during the conference
- Liaise with prospective and secured sponsors for ISMIR 2021 and Women in MIR
- Oversee the financial exchange (money, receipts) between the conference organization and the sponsors

The chairs divided the full list of prospective sponsors roughly into three and acted as the point of contact. Alia Morsi and Sertan Şentürk focused on defining roles and responsibilities, sponsorship packages, coordinating volunteers, supervising the implementation of sponsorship benefits. During the conference, they were in charge of the events in Conference Session A. Hanoi Hantrakul focused on implementing and hosting the industry panels and masterclasses. During the conference, he was in charge of the events in Conference Session B.

In addition, 13 volunteers assisted the co-chairs. The volunteers helped in various ways, such as transcribing & post-processing pre-recorded material, populating sponsorship content in virtual platforms, and helping the co-chairs with logistics during the conference.

A rough timeline of the Industry & Sponsorship work is given below:

- February to March: Set up core team, handover from 2020 chairs, define responsibilities
- April: Define sponsorship packages, define types of sessions in the conference program, initial comms with past sponsors
- May: 1st call for sponsors, start onboarding sponsors
- June to July: Implement Industry and Sponsorship sessions in the program
- August to September: The second call for sponsors, invite speakers to the Industry sessions
- September to October: Supervise the implementation of sponsorship benefits and virtual spaces, finalize sessions, onboard volunteers
- November: Freeze the sponsors, conference in action

Sponsorship packages

The Industry and Sponsorship team handled onboarding Sponsors for the main conference and Women in MIR (WiMIR). The official calls were announced on the ISMIR mailing list and social media. The co-chairs also contacted past and potential sponsors directly. The announcements for the main conference were carried out by the Industry and Sponsorship co-chairs, whereas Diversity and Inclusion co-chairs took care of the WiMIR announcements. The Social Media chair managed the social media announcements.

The sponsorship packages were updated as we had more clarity on the conference program and the virtual platform. Please see the *Call for Sponsorship Page* (<https://ismir2021.ismir.net/cfs/>) for the final sponsorship packages and benefits.

Below we provide a summary of ISMIR and WiMIR Sponsorships:

Main Conference: ISMIR 2021 had three tiers of Sponsorship packages, namely: Platinum (10,000\$), Gold (5,500\$), Silver (2,500\$). We made two official calls for the main conference, on 7 May and 1 August 2021.

The economic uncertainties during the pandemic negatively impacted the Sponsorship activities in ISMIR 2020. According to the feedback from the ISMIR 2020 chairs and Sponsors, we made several updates to the sponsorship packages and benefits. The major changes were:

- Reduced package pricing for each tier by around 10-15% to attract more sponsors.
- Added CV pool and Job Board as new sponsorship benefits to all Tiers
- Removed Bronze Tier and re-defined Silver Tier with the option to host a virtual booth or give an Industry Presentation in the Program.

The Industry and Sponsorship team had conversations with around 60 companies. Among these, 20 companies (1/3 conversion rate) were onboarded as Sponsors (2 Platinum, 4 Gold, 14 Silver) to the main conference.¹ Nine of these Sponsors were first-timers. The list of Conference Sponsors is available at <https://ismir2021.ismir.net/sponsors/>.

Women in MIR (WiMIR) Sponsorship: This year had three tiers, namely Patron (5,000\$ and above), Contributor (2,500-4,999\$), Supporter (1000-2499\$). 7 Sponsors contributed to Women in MIR (1 Patron, 5 Contributor, 1 Supporter), listed at <https://ismir2021.ismir.net/wimir/>.

The table below presents a breakdown of the income from Sponsorship.

¹ Note that 19 sponsors are listed on the website. One company joined as a Silver Sponsor on the condition that their contribution is directed towards the Late-Breaking Demos as part of Diversity and Inclusion efforts. They didn't want to be announced.

Income	# Sponsors	Amount
ISMIR conference sponsorship	19	71,000\$
Women in MIR sponsorship	7	19,000 \$
Late-breaking demos	1	2500 \$
Total		92,500 \$

In addition, some Sponsors contributed to best paper awards and trivia social awards in the form of software, access to their services, and user subscriptions.

Below you can find the sponsorship income and the number of sponsors for the main conference (i.e., excluding WiMIR sponsorship) by tier in the last five years.

To the best of our knowledge, ISMIR 2021 has seen the most sponsors and largest sponsorship income than all ISMIR conferences in the past. But, more importantly, we managed to increase the revenue by 40% and onboard five additional sponsors compared to ISMIR 2020, effectively returning the sponsor presence in the conference back to the pre-pandemic levels.

Industry Sessions

The Industry and Sponsorship co-chairs organized eight sessions in the conference program, which around 1000 people attended. All of the sessions were in broadcasted live via Zoom during the conference. They were run only once, i.e., not replicated in the other time-zone, primarily due to the unavailability of the panelists. The sessions were shared during the conference with the Attendees to watch on-demand.

Below we provide a summary of the sessions. For more information, please refer to the ISMIR 2021 Proceedings.

Industry Presentations are sessions where sponsors showcase their company's MIR work and research. ISMIR 2021 program had four Industry presentation sessions. Two of these were dedicated to the Platinum Sponsors each, and the other two were shared by Gold and (if the optional benefit was selected) Silver sponsors.

Industry Panels are sessions about applications of MIR in industrial products and their (ethical, societal, technological, financial, etc.) impact. The ISMIR 2021 program had two panels: 1) *MIR Technologies and Education* and 2) *MIR Technologies Across Cultures*. The panels were implemented as roundtable discussions and moderated by two established academicians working on these topics. Half of the panelists were recommended to the moderator from the employees of the Sponsors in Platinum and Gold tiers that operate in a relevant area. The moderator invited the rest of the panelists among academicians and industry practitioners.

Masterclasses are sessions where participants discuss topics related to getting into and working in the industry. These sessions are not tied to sponsorship, i.e., the panelists were approached independent of their companies' participation in the conference. ISMIR 2021 program had two masterclasses: 1) *CV Masterclass* and 2) *Systems Design Interview Masterclass*. The masterclasses were implemented as described below:

- **CV Masterclass:** One of the sponsorship co-chairs hosted the CV masterclass with an audio tech recruiter. They gave feedback on CVs shared by volunteers.
- **Systems Design Interview:** A mock interview was recorded in advance at a single take, with a Senior Engineer acting as the interviewee and two of the Co-Chairs acting as the lead and shadow interviewers, respectively. The video was post-processed minimally and transcribed to English. During the live session, the participants of the mock interview first gave a short presentation on Systems Design interviews, played the video back, followed by a Q&A.

The below table summarizes the number of sessions, participants, and attendees:

Industry Session Type	# Sessions	Participants	Attendance
Industry Presentation	4 Sessions	11 Sponsors	115 people on average; ~660 in total
Industry Panel	2 Sessions	1 Host (one of the Co-chairs), 1 Moderator, and 5 Panelists in each session; 14 participants in total	65 people on average; ~130 in total
Masterclass	2 Sessions	2 and 3 panelists in the sessions, respectively; 5 participants in total	90 people on average; ~180 in total

Sponsorship Spaces

During the conference, Platinum, Gold, and some Silver Sponsors (if they selected the optional benefit) had virtual booths on the conference platform. The Sponsors were free to populate static material into the booth, such as company presentations, videos, and links to job posts. The booths also had text chat and video room, where each Sponsor can interact with the conference attendees, typically in “live hours” they announced in advance.

The virtual platform also consisted of a job board, where all Sponsors could post open internships and job posts. There was a link to a CV pool on top of the Job Board page, which 73 conference attendees used to upload their CVs via Google Forms. The CVs were sent to the sponsor representatives at the end of the conference.

The below table summarizes the virtual sponsorship spaces and their usage:

Space	Used By	Attendee Participation
Sponsor Booth	13 Sponsors	Not tracked
Job Board	Internship and Permanent Positions Advertised by 12 Sponsors Note that there was a separate job board for academic positions.	Not tracked
CV Drop-off	CVs sent to 18 Sponsors	73 Attendees submitted their CVs

Code of Conduct

Similar to the past years, the Sponsors were obliged to follow the conference [Code of Conduct](#). No violations were reported in ISMIR 2021 regarding Industry and Sponsorship activities.

Post-Conference Survey

We sent a survey to the ISMIR and WiMIR Sponsors just after the conference. We received thirteen responses, five of which are from companies that sponsored both ISMIR and WiMIR. Below we summarize the feedback:

The sponsors were overall highly satisfied by the Industry and Sponsorship work in the conference.

The main conference Sponsors were typically satisfied with how the benefits were implemented. Nevertheless, several Sponsors expressed that virtual booths, the Industry panel, and the CV pool were less effective. Specifically, some Sponsors complained about the navigation to the Industry and Sponsorship spaces in the virtual platform and the difficulty of interacting with attendees in virtual booths.

The WiMIR Sponsors were typically satisfied with the WiMIR / Diversity & Inclusion benefits. However, two of five respondents indicated that the benefits did not fully help them in their efforts to hire from a diverse pool of candidates.

The respondents mostly anticipate sponsoring the main conference next year. Current WiMIR Sponsors plan to sponsor next year's initiative as well. Having said that, companies that only sponsored the main conference are not typically interested in extending their support to WiMIR Sponsorship in 2022.

Suggestions for future conferences

To conclude, we share some of our recommendations and ideas suggested by the sponsors in the post-conference feedback survey.

Team composition and responsibilities:

- Having three co-chairs allowed us to distribute the workload efficiently and helped to broaden our outreach to prospective sponsors throughout the year. Therefore, we advise **keeping the number of chairs at three** in ISMIR 2022.
- During the conference, it would be good to establish **three points of contact** (ideally the co-chairs themselves) to fulfill the hybrid requirements of ISMIR 2022:
 - The “main” point of contact physically at the conference site, responsible for the coordination
 - Two additional points of contact; one around UTC+0, and another around UTC -8 or UTC +9, focusing on the virtual activities
- Masterclasses were not tied to Sponsorship benefits, and the panelists were invited independently. We would advise **having separate chair(s) for masterclasses** - similar to ISMIR 2020.

Onboarding:

- Limit platinum sponsors and gold sponsors according to the organization's capacity (e.g., two platinum and five gold sponsors at most)
- Stop onboarding sponsors at least two weeks before the conference
- Freeze the program at least three weeks before the conference

Benefits:

- The availability of the panelists at the sessions may change. Ask the Sponsors to name a substitute up-front.

- The job board and CV pool were very well received by both the Sponsors and the attendees. Several first-timers contacted us directly for Sponsorship just after the job board announcement. We would suggest keeping these benefits.
- The virtual platform should allow the organizers to upload the content and layout from Sponsors with minimum intervention.

Suggestions from Sponsors:

- Improve the user experience in the conference platform, particularly in conference booths. One responder noted the potential need to bridge a communication gap between attendees & Sponsors that occurred in some hybrid conferences during the pandemic.
- Introduce a call-for-papers for Industry presentations, with a separate review process.
- Attendees should be able to select the Sponsors when submitting to the CV pool. This way, personal information will be shared only with the consented Sponsors, and the Sponsors will not need to review CVs from uninterested applicants.
- Investigate how D&I benefits could facilitate better hiring opportunities for a diverse group of attendees.

Acknowledgments

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Last but not least, a sincere thanks to the [Sponsors of ISMIR 2021](#) not only for their generous support but also for all the contributions to the proliferation of the MIR community.